

Electrochemical investigations of kinetics and mechanism of oxidation of caffeic acid in aqueous media using glassy carbon/multi-walls carbon nanotubes modified electrode

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Abstract : Electrochemical investigation of kinetics and mechanism of caffeic acid oxidation was carried out in aqueous phosphate solutions with different pH values. Bare glassy carbon, GC and GC-modified with multi-walls carbon nanotubes, MWCNTs electrodes were used. Markedly improved cyclic voltammetric responses, giving rise to chemically reversible, concerted two-electron oxidation process, were obtained when MWCNTs/GC electrode is used. Importantly, the oxidation behaviour is a function of scan rate, concentration, and pH-dependent. The mechanism is consistent with the transfer of two electrons coupled with two protons. It was concluded that caffeic acid oxidizes chemically following ECEC, radical-radical mechanism. The proposed mechanism was confirmed on comparing the experimental data with the simulated ones.

Keywords : Caffeic acid, cyclic voltammetry, chronoamperometry, chronocoulometry, digital simulation.

Introduction

Caffeic acid, *trans*-3-(3,4-dihydroxyphenyl) propenoic acid, is a naturally occurring organic compound that is found in all plants as a key intermediate in the biosynthesis of lignin¹. Owing to the highly antioxidant activities²⁻⁴ and potential effects on human health, caffeic acid and its phenethyl ester derivatives have been shown to exhibit potential activity against HIV integrase and can also inhibit HIV replication with moderate anti-HIV activity in cell culture⁵. Thus, knowledge concerning the redox chemistry of caffeic acid is crucial to understand the behaviour in biological environments. For this reason, the oxidative behaviour of caffeic acid was the subject of intensive investigations in literature. For instance, its electrochemical oxidation was studied in various media including nonaqueous media e.g. acetonitrile⁶, aqueous solutions with different pH's⁷⁻¹⁵, and in aqueous acetate-ethanol or water-acetone mixtures⁹⁻¹². Importantly, enhanced electrochemical responses for caffeic acid oxidation-reduction processes were observed upon modification of the working electrode surface with single-walled carbon nanotube, SWCNTs^{10,11}.

The majority of these electrochemical studies have suggested that the oxidation of CAF may involve the transfer of two electrons and two protons per molecule following an ECEC mechanism. However, these studies provided neither full details nor solid proof of the aforementioned mechanism. Thus, in this contribution, in continuation of our study of the electrochemical investigation on polyphenol antioxidants¹⁶, a detail electrochemical investigation of kinetics and mechanism of caffeic acid in aqueous phosphate buffers using multi-walls carbon nanotubes, modified glassy carbon, MWCNTs/GC, electrode was carried out. The mechanism is proposed according to the data obtained by cyclic voltammetry, double step chronoamperometry and chronocoulometry and is confirmed by digital simulation.

Experimental

Caffeic acid (P99%) was purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. The MWCNTs purity : >90%; carbon basis, D × L 110-170 nm × 5-9 μm from Aldrich. All other used solutions were prepared from BDH analytical grade chemicals. 0.2 M phosphate buffer supporting electrolyte

was prepared with different pH values from monosodium phosphate and disodium phosphate in deionized water. Fresh stock solution (5 mM) of H₃CAF was prepared from the substrate in the phosphate buffer. The analyzed solutions were prepared by dilution just before use. A conventional three-electrode electrolytic cell was employed, in which saturated calomel electrode, SCE, a platinum electrode were used as reference and counter electrodes, respectively. Glassy carbon/multi-walls carbon nanotubes modified electrode, MWCNTs/GCE was employed as a working electrode.

1.0 mg ml⁻¹ suspension of MWCNTs was obtained on dispersing five milligrams MWCNTs in 5.0 ml *N,N*-dimethylformamide (DMF). The mixed solution was ultrasonically agitated for 6 h. The MWCNTs/GCE electrode was prepared by drop 1.0 ml of MWCNTs suspension (1.0 mg mL⁻¹) onto the clean surface of GCE. Then the solvent was evaporated overnight. The glassy carbon electrode was polished with 0.5 μm alumina powder on a polishing cloth. After rinsing the surface with deionized water, the polished GCE was sonicated for 5 min in water/ethanol to get rid of trace amounts of alumina powder from the surface and rinsed again with deionized water. Then, the surface was fully dried at atmospheric condition with a stream of purified nitrogen. Test solutions were degassed with pure nitrogen prior to the electrochemical measurements. A nitrogen blanket was maintained thereafter. All experiments were performed at room temperature (25 °C). The electrochemical experiments were performed with an EG & G Princeton Applied Research Model 273A potentiostat/Galvanostat controlled by a computer. The electrochemical experiments were controlled by PC and the electrochemical set-up was controlled with an EG & G Princeton Applied Research Model M 270 software. Background data were stored and subtracted from the experimental data set, minimizing side effects such as double layer charging current.

Results and discussion

Cyclic voltammetry :

The cyclic voltammograms of phosphate buffer solution (pH 2.21) containing 98.0 μM caffeic acid, CAF, at a bare and at MWCNTs-modified GCE at scan rate of 50

mV s⁻¹ are shown in Fig. 1. The cyclic voltammograms exhibit an anodic peak at ≈ 0.50 with cathodic peak at reverse scan, indicating that the CV involves a reversible redox process. It can be seen that the CAF oxidation peak at the bare GCE is weak and broad while the response is considerably improved at the MWCNTs-modified GCE. At the modified electrode, the oxidation peak is considerably enhanced in its peak current. This was attributed to the electro-catalytic effect caused by MWCNTs¹⁶. Meanwhile the MWCNTs increase the effective area of the electrode.

Fig. 1. Cyclic voltammograms of 98.0 μM CAF on bare GCE (solid line) and MWCNTs/GCE modified electrode (dotted line) in 0.2 M phosphate buffer solution (pH 2.21), scan rate : 50 mV s⁻¹.

At pH 2.21, the value of $E_{pa} - E_{pa/2} = 42$ mV at scan rate 20 mV. It is high; it should be close to 30 mV for a reversible two-electron transfer system. The difference between the obtained and expected value indicates, however, that the charge transfer is not sufficiently fast under such conditions and that reaction is not completely reversible. On increasing scan rate, the redox peak current of CAF increase and correlate linearly with the square root of scan rate, $v^{1/2}$, with regression coefficient, r , of 0.999. This means that electrochemical oxidation of CAF is diffusion-controlled process. The peak current ratio (i_{pc}/i_{pa}) is nearly unity, can be considered as a criterion for the stability of oxidized product produced at the surface of the electrode under the experimental conditions.

On increasing scan rate, the oxidation peak potential, E_{pa} , of CAF is anodically shifted showing a linear varia-

tion with the logarithm of the scan rate according to the following relation :

$$E_{pa} = -19.9 + 36.7 \log v \quad r = 0.967 \quad (1)$$

The $\partial E_{pa}/\partial \log v$ of 36.7 mV/decade consistent with a radical-radical dimerization mechanism, since it has been previously reported that dimeric species can be formed during the chemical and electrochemical oxidation of neutral and dianionic hydroxycinnamic acid, respectively^{17,18}. Moreover, a plot of the peak current function, $i_{pa}/v^{1/2}$, and peak current ratio, i_{pc}/i_{pa} , as a function of scan rate is in a good agreement with occurrence of a chemical reaction following the electron transfer process appearing as a gradual diminish in the $i_{pa}/v^{1/2}$ and a decrease the i_{pc}/i_{pa} with increasing scan rate¹⁸.

Fig. 2 represents the effect of CAF concentration on CV responses. The peak currents of anodic CV wave, i_{pa} , show a linear variation with concentration of CAF. It gives linear least-squares relation with correlation coefficient of 0.996. This confirms that the CV wave is purely diffusion-controlled process. Furthermore, the peak current ratio, i_{pc}/i_{pa} , decreases and the anodic and cathodic peaks are shifted on increasing concentration. This clearly

Fig. 2. Cyclic voltammograms of CAF on MWCNTs/GCE in 0.2 M phosphate buffer solution (pH 2.21) at different CAF concentrations. Scan rate : 20 mV s⁻¹.

shows that the chemical reaction is presumably second order. The present results therefore indicate that the electrode process involves a dimerization reaction¹⁹.

Cyclic voltammograms 98.0 μM solution of caffeic

acid in solutions with various pHs are shown in Fig. 3. It is observed that the profile of the CV is the same in the pH range of investigation, indicating that the electrochemical-oxidation of CAF follows the same reaction mechanism. However, on increasing the pH of solution, the anodic and cathodic peak potentials are shifted toward less positive values. This indicates that hydrogen ions participate in the electrode reaction. The values of anodic peak potentials, E_{pa} , as a function of solution's pH are plotted. It is found that E_{pa} is shifted to negative potentials with a slope of about -69 mV/pH with correlation

Fig. 3. Cyclic voltammograms of 98.0 μM CAF in 0.2 M phosphate buffer solution at various pH values 2.21, 3.95, 5.06, 7.10 and 10.18, respectively at scan rate of 20 mV s⁻¹.

coefficient of -0.999. This value is close to that expected for Nernstian systems with electron transfer followed by deprotonation. This is expected because CAF has a catechol ring with two-electron two-proton redox behaviour¹⁵. At higher pH's, > 10.2, the cathodic wave disappears, revealing that under such conditions, the generated product is not stable.

Taking into account the above findings and the literature survey, the oxidation mechanism for CAF is proposed to follows Scheme 1. In this mechanisms, protonation/deprotonation processes are not separately described, being treated together with electron-transfer in single steps. This is because such processes are generally too fast to be limiting processes. The mechanism involves a loss of one electron follows by a fast deprotonation reaction giv-

ing semiquinone radical, A^\bullet . This semiquinone radical intermediate plays an important role in the oxidation of CAF. The semiquinone radical reacts with another one to produce a radical-radical dimer, B. The next step is the loss of a second electron to yield the dimer radical cation, $B^{\bullet+}$, which deprotonates to the final oxidation product, D.

Scheme 1

Double potential step chronoamperometry and chronocoulometry :

Double potential step chronoamperometry is used to study the electron transfer processes coupled with chemical reaction mechanisms. In 0.2 M phosphate buffer solution (pH 2.12), the chronoamperograms of 98.0 μ M caffeic acid are recorded at different duration times. In absence of coupled chemical reaction, it is expected that the anodic current, i_a , after stepping potential from initial value E_i to a final value E_f , where CAF is electrochemically inactive, equals the cathodic current, i_c , in the second step after duration time τ , where the electrode reaction proceeds. Chronoamperograms obtained for CAF show a decrease in i_c/i_a ratio on increasing time. This indicates a consumption of the electron transfer products in the following chemical reaction at long time (EC mechanism).

Double potential step chronocoulometric experiments are carried out to determine the diffusion coefficients, D , of caffeic acid and deduce the current nature.

According to the following equation,

$$Q(t < \tau) = \frac{2nFAD^{1/2}C^*_{\text{bulk}}}{\pi^{1/2}} t^{1/2} \quad (2)$$

where D ($\text{cm}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$) is diffusion coefficient, C^*_{bulk} (mol/

cm^3) is bulk the concentration of species, τ is the step duration time, n is number of electron, F (C/mol) is the Faraday constant, and A (cm^2) is the area of the electrode, the parameter D can be calculated from the slope of Q versus $t^{1/2}$ plot. The charge of the first step, $Q(t < \tau)$, is unaffected by the chemical reaction, so that it is used to estimate the diffusion coefficient. The chronocoulograms of CAF in 0.2 M phosphate buffer solution (pH 2.12) are obtained at different duration times. On plotting $Q(t < \tau)$ versus $t^{1/2}$, straight regression lines are obtained with regression coefficients of 0.9994 for all used duration times. This reveals that the oxidation of caffeic acid is diffusion-controlled process over the entire range of time. From the slope, the value of D is obtained. The mean value of D is estimated to be $9.35 \times 10^{-6} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$.

Digital simulation :

A proposed scheme for the electrochemical oxidation of CAF is tested by digital simulation. On the basis of Scheme 1, the observed homogeneous and heterogeneous parameters for the electron transfer and chemical processes are determined on comparing the simulation results with the experimental cyclic voltammograms (Fig. 4). The simulation results are obtained on performing a set of simulations, i.e. different ECEC mechanisms including ECEC radical-radical dimer; ECEC parent-radical dimer, and ECEC first-order are tested. The simulation results are carried out employing the DigSim 3.03

Fig. 4. Best fit for experimental and digital simulated cyclic voltammograms for the oxidation of 98.0 μ M CAF on MWCNT/GCE in 0.2 M phosphate buffer solution (pH 2.21) at scan rate of 10 mV/s following ECEC, radical-radical mechanism.

Table 1. Homogeneous and heterogeneous parameters for the electrochemical oxidation of 98.0 mM caffeic acid following ECEC radical-radical mechanism on MWCNT/GCE in 0.2 M phosphate buffer solution (pH 2.21) at scan rate of 10 mV/s

E°_1 (mV)	E°_2 (mV)	k°_1 (cm s ⁻¹)	α_1	k°_2 (cm s ⁻¹)	α_2	K_{c1}		K_{c2}		
						k_f (L/mol s)	k_b (L/mol s)	k_f (L/mol s)	k_b (L/mol s)	
461	303	0.002	0.5	6.4×10^{-5}	0.75	5.29×10^{-15}	4.71×10^{-17}	3.04×10^{-7}	5.17×10^{-6}	16.96

software. The formal potential E°_1 is obtained experimentally as the average of the anodic and cathodic peak potentials observed in CAF cyclic voltammetry. The second formal potential E°_2 is suggested to be more or less E°_1 . The diffusion coefficient D is, as determined above, 9.35×10^{-6} cm² s⁻¹. The transfer coefficient, α , is assumed to be 0.5 throughout. The procedure is performed based on achieving the best fit between simulated and experimental cyclic voltammograms. Fig. 4 shows in open symbols represent the simulated voltammogram. From the results obtained, it is clear that the simulated curve fits the experimental one. The kinetic parameter data obtained are depicted in Table 1. Thus, the simulation using the concluded ECEC, radical-radical mechanism agrees well with the above proposed mechanism given in Scheme 1.

Conclusion :

Caffeic acid is electrochemically oxidised in aqueous phosphate on glassy carbon electrode modified with multi-walls carbon nanotubes, MWCNTs/GCE. It gives a two-electron oxidation process reversible cyclic voltammetric response. The oxidation behaviour is a function of scan rate, concentration, and pH-dependent. The electrode reaction follows ECEC, radical-radical mechanism. The proposed mechanism was confirmed on comparing the experimental data with the simulated ones.

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